

THE THIRD RENESSAINCE UZBEKISTAN EXPANDS OPPORTUNITY FOR A FURTHER RISE IN THE INTERNATIONAL INNOVATION INDEX

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Abstract. This article is devoted to the comprehensive analysis of the results of the ranking of Uzbekistan in the Global Innovation Index (GII-2021) by the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) in 2021 and seven indicators used for achieving this rating. In addition, this article offers proposals for further improvement of some indicators, including low business attractiveness (Business sophistication), Creative outputs and research and technological results (Knowledge & technology outputs). Moreover, the article presents the views expressed on the issues that need to be settled in the implementation of the priorities set out in the “Concept of Science Development until 2030”, as well as relevant conclusions developed in the process of the research.

Keywords: innovation index, institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market attractiveness, business attractiveness, scientific and technological results, creative output.

Introduction

The Decree “On Approval of the Strategy of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2021” adopted in Uzbekistan three years ago on September 21, 2018 states that: “...our country is not participating in the ranking of the Global Innovation Index, compiled in recent years by influential and reputable international organizations”.

“The changes that have been launched in our country will not be reversed ... despite the challenges experienced nowadays, we are able to adapt to difficult conditions and find new “points for growth”-said Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

Over the past two years, as a result of the implementation of the priorities set in this Decree, Uzbekistan with its economy in 2020 is the only country in Central Asia ranked 93rd in the Global Innovation Index (GII).

It is known that last year in the ranking of indicators of the Global Innovation Index (GII-2021) published by the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) under the heading “Monitoring innovations through the crisis COVID-19” Uzbekistan ranked 86th among 132 countries, thus going up 7 points compared to

2020! It should be noted that in the first attempt made in 2020, Uzbekistan scored 93 points in this ranking. So, the sayings of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev, which could manage to inspire confidence in our people for the future, are being currently proved.

Uzbekistan aims to be among the top 50 in the Global Innovation Index in 2030. Despite the short period of time, it is worth being proud of the results. First of all, our country entered this ranking in 2020 and ranked 93, and then in 2021 it has improved by 7 points and ranked 86. Moreover, it should be noted that at the meeting of the Republican Council on International Ratings and Indices on December 23, 2021, it was emphasized that our position in the Global Innovation Index has improved and there is much work ahead to be done in this regard. Nevertheless, it is a great and historic achievement for the Uzbek economy, which has not been included in the rankings for the last decade. Herewith we would like to say that if we make an effort, we will definitely achieve our goals.

Literature review

K. Sveiby [14] considered the concepts of intellectual property and intellectual capital and in his model he divided a company's intangible assets (intellectual property) into three groups: external structure (trade mark, image of the company and production recognition), competence of employees (education, intellectual knowledge, experience and skills), internal structure (patent, copyright, management systems, databases and scientific developments). As it is obvious from this model, intellectual property objects are represented only in the external and internal structures of the company. We do not fully agree with this model as it entirely covered intellectual property objects and approached thereto as intangible assets. If they were intangible assets, the K. Sveiby's model would require a close (alignment) approach to accounting objects.

From the point of view of Thomas P. Carlin [15], intellectual property represents an ambiguous item in the balance which has a poor quality. In his research he made an emphasis on the value of intellectual property as a key component of intangible assets and justified an opportunity for their assessment. In our opinion, if intellectual property objects had more efficient opportunities for their use, it could be possible to turn into the most profitable asset item of the balance.

B. Leontyev [16] refers intellectual property to the intellectual capital. In addition, he specifies that intellectual property consists of the value of all available assets, intellectual novelties, knowledge, opportunities, and consolidated base of knowledge.

I. Ivanov [18] considers the concept of intellectual property in terms of the exclusive right of a person to the results of intellectual activity and specifies that it consists of a trademark, a company name, a brand name, and a service mark. He

summarizes his views and comes to the conclusion that intellectual property is a part of these intangible assets.

L. Lytneva [19] evaluates intellectual property as a component of intangible assets and proposes to divide it into the following groups: industrial property objects, objects of copyright and tools for individualization of goods. This classification is practically close to international practice and is grouped according to the intellectual property used by companies.

R. Ducmuratov [24] developed the method of recording and auditing intellectual property objects as intangible assets. I. Icmaynov [20] touched upon the issues of transformation of intellectual property objects to the international standards of financial reports as assets that require special attention in accounting. Sh. Ilkhamov [21] studied intellectual property objects according to the criteria for recognition of long-term assets. M. Polatov [12] Based on the Brooking model, he studied the ability to record and audit these objects as a component of the enterprise's intellectual capital. Supporting the opinion of A. Poltorak and P. Lerner, I. Davletov [22] highlighted the aspects of acquisition and audit of intellectual property objects in the agrarian sphere. In M. Pardaev's [23] scientific works and published publications, models and indicators of the analysis of intellectual property objects as a component of intangible assets have been formed.

Methodology

Such research methods as induction and deduction, analysis and synthesis, systematic approach, logical thinking, comparison, factor analysis have been applied in the study of the results of the rating of the position and indicators of Uzbekistan in the Global Innovation Index. Herewith the data on indicators have been analyzed in a comprehensive manner and relevant conclusions have been developed using comparative analysis methods.

Results and discussion

In this regard, there may arise the question, by which indicators Uzbekistan has achieved a worthy rank in this prestigious rating. As mentioned above, this rating is developed in reliance upon certain criteria. However, the main goal of the Innovation Development Strategy, set by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in line with the world economic development, is to “develop human capital”. Thus, as a result of achieving the main goal of the Strategy, according to the Global Innovation Index, Uzbekistan must become one of the 50 strongest countries in the world by 2030. This can be evaluated and recognized as a key factor in determining the level of competitiveness and innovative development of the country in the international arena.

In this regard we are proud to note, that Uzbekistan has become one of the top five countries in Central and South Asia (India ranked 46, the Islamic Republic of

Iran ranked 60, Kazakhstan ranked 79, Uzbekistan ranked 86 and Kyrgyzstan ranked 98). However, Uzbekistan is still considered a lower-middle income country (*LM = lower-middle income*).

According to the indicators of 2021, Uzbekistan ranked 10 in the “Income” category and 4 in “Regional Rating” and attained a total of 27.4 scores. The figures demonstrate that the Global Innovation Index of Uzbekistan in 2021 has risen by 2.4 scores (27.4) (in 2020 it was rated from 0-100 to 25.0). Thus, according to the Global Innovation Index (GII-2021), Uzbekistan is ranked according to the following indicators: rating in GII-2021 - 86, entry rating - 100, exit rating - 75, income level - below average - 10, region - Central and South Asia, on GDP purchasing power parity (PPP) -250.2 billion USD, GDP per capita (RRR) -7.4 thousand USD.

It is well known that on December 28, 2021 the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan participated in the informal CIS summit. CIS countries are also ranked in the GII-2021, including Russia ranked 45, Belarus ranked 62, Armenia ranked 69 and Azerbaijan ranked 80. What we mean is that the increase in Uzbekistan activity with the CIS countries in recent years (signing of more than 40 beneficial agreements, membership in 23 influential CIS organizations) can guarantee a further increase in our international rankings.

In terms of Central Asia, we are still ranked 2 (Kazakhstan ranked 79, downgrading two scores compared to 2020, Kyrgyzstan ranked 98 downgrading four scores. Like our country, Tajikistan has achieved a favourable result, being ranked 103, improving its position by 6 scores). This means that while our country remains second in Central Asia, there is almost a decline in neighboring countries, and the rise is not at our level.

Table 1

Uzbekistan in Global Innovation Index (GII-2021)

Assessment score (0-100)	Rank	Income	CSA	Rank in the region
27.4	86	Low-middle (LM)	Central and South Asia	4

This means that it will be absolutely leading country over the next 2-3 years and not doubt, our country will have been able to enter the top 50 by 2026 (if the average increase accounts for 2.4 scores, it will constitute 9.6 in 4 years or 37.0 in total), while the lower limit of TOP-50 of the GII-2021 is equal to 35.4 scores. This proves the fact that the goal can be achieved only due to progress, knowledge, research, innovation, creativity, and so on. In our opinion, we will achieve this in reliance upon the “Third Renaissance”, which has laid the foundation of the New Awakening period in our country.

Below we try to find the answers to the question which indicators of Uzbekistan have promoted 7-score increase in the ranking of the Global Innovation Index. This can be obvious from the data on the 7 most important indicators (components).

Table 2

Position of Uzbekistan in the indicators of the Global Innovation Index (GII-2021)

№	Indicators	Rating result
In GII-2021 rating: Uzbekistan ranked 86 (ranked 93 in 2020)		
1.	Institutions	ranked 94 (ranked 95 in 2020)
2.	Human capital & research	ranked 72 (ranked 77 in 2020)
3.	Infrastructure	ranked 72 (ranked 77 in 2020)
4.	Market sophistication	ranked 24 (ranked 27 in 2020)
5.	Business sophistication	ranked 123 (ranked 127 in 2020)
6.	Knowledge & technology outputs	ranked 77 (ranked 90 in 2020)
7.	Creative outputs	ranked 113 (ranked 127 in 2020)

Below, we provide an analysis of which data they have used to receive rating scores for each indicator.

If we consider the data on the first indicator, in the “Institutions” category there has been an increase by one score from 95 to 94 (55.8 scores) and herewith assessment has been made according to the following parameters:

first, the political environment constitutes 47.6 scores or ranked 95 (political and operational stability - 64.3/80, government efficiency - 39.2/99),

second, the legislative base accounts for 49.9 scores or ranked 107 (quality of laws -17.5 126, the law priority- 19.1/123, dismissal costs -17.3/69),

third, the business environment amounts to 69.8 scores or ranked 72 (ease of starting a business 96.2/8, ease of resolving insolvency -43.5/90).

As it has been noted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, one should admit, we have a lot of work to do to further strengthen the legislative framework of the republic and ensure its supremacy. In turn, this rating demonstrates weakness of our legal framework (ranked 107). The Assembly of the Republican Council for International Ratings and Indices have also identified special measures to improve the international rating in this political and legal sphere in 2022. We are proud of the fact, that in terms of this parameter, our performance in the business environment is assessed as strong (ranked 72).

In the second indicator, Human Capital & Research, there has been 5 score increase to 30.4 and ranked 72:

first, no data is available in terms of education, which accounts for 57.3 scores or ranked 42 (education costs - 5.3 percent in relation to GDP or ranked 28, no data available on public funding/student in percent in relation to GDP, secondary education (school) duration, year constitutes 12.5/87, international student assessment program PISA scale - no data available, student-teacher ratio, average - 10.9/37),

second, higher education accounts for 32.0 scores or ranked 68 (enrollment in higher education, gross percentage - 12.6/108, graduates in science and engineering, percentage - 34.5/7, mobility in higher education - 0.2/105),

third, research and development (R&D) 2.0 scores or ranked 95 (researchers, FTE-full-time equivalent/person - 476.2/69, research and development expenditures in relation to GDP, in percent - 0.1/99, research and investors, million USD - 0.0/41, QS- university rating - 0.0/74).

In this parameter there are few positive cases due to insufficient or inadequate information provided. These include the international student assessment program PISA scale and government funding/student in relation to GDP, etc. However, in the ranking, the student-teacher ratio and the performance of graduates in science and engineering are recognized as strong (ranked 7, while Russia ranked 13, Kazakhstan - 46).

The third parameter in the ranking - Infrastructure - also rose by 5 points compared to 2020, from 77 to 72 (40.4 scores).

According to this, first, information and communication technologies (ICT) constituted 66.9 scores or ranked 65 (access to ICT 60.1/76, use of ICT 48.3/84, online government service - 78.2/46, electronic users 81.0/46),

second, general infrastructure accounts for 35.7 scores or ranked 37 (electricity generation - 1908.6/82, logistics - 24.6/95, gross capital formation in percent in relation to GDP - 39.5/7),

third, ecological balance accounts for 18.7 scores or ranked 111 (GDP/energy consumption unit 5.8/110, environmental impact - 44.3/77, ISO 14001 environmental certificates/billion USD in relation to GDP - 0.2/116). According to some of these indicators, we are in the top 50, for example, ranked 46 by online services of our government! In terms of e-commerce, we possess the same result and according to the level of capital formation in relation to GDP we can even compete for the top 10, as we ranked 7! (Russia ranked 59, Kazakhstan ranked 24). In general, our indicators of "Infrastructure" have demonstrated their strengths in many parameters.

"Market sophistication" is considered another important indicator of the global rating, which has shown an increase by 3 points. In other words, this indicator accounts for 56.9 scores or ranked 24.

First, the lending is rated at 30.2 scores or ranked 105 (ease of borrowing - 65.0/61, domestic loans to the private sector in percent in relation to GDP - 30.0/95, microfinance gross loans in percent in relation to GDP - 0.0/80),

second, investments have been rated at 70.0 scores or incomplete data (ease of protection of minority investors - 70.0/36, market capitalization- no data available, venture capital investors, transactions/billion USD - no data available, venture capital recipients, transactions/ billion USD - no data available),

third, trade, diversification and market size have been rated at 70.4 or ranked 62 (applicable tariff rate, average weight, 8.7/110, local industry diversification - 95.9/22, domestic market size, billion USD (PPP) - 250.2/60). In these indicators, we ranked 22 in the rating, especially as a result of the favourable actions done on the diversification of local industry at the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This is something to be proud of at the international level, and even shows that we are an absolute leader among the CIS countries (Belarus ranked 41, Russia ranked 44, Azerbaijan ranked 71, Tajikistan ranked 74, Kazakhstan ranked 87, Kyrgyzstan ranked 101).

According to “Business sophistication”, the fifth indicator of the rating in 2021 it has increased by 4 points compared to 2020 (improved its position from 127 ranking to 123 ranking).

Herewith, the first, educated employees have been rated at 22.8 scores, or the rating data is incomplete [93] (knowledge-intensive employment - no data available, firms offering formal training - 16.9/87% compared to GERD in relation to GDP - 0.1/72, GERD funded by business in relation to GDP - 42.4/38, women with academic degree- no data available),

second, innovation relations have been scored at 2.6 or [130], data is inadequate (university-industry collaboration-data on research is not available, development status of the cluster - no data available, foreign-funded GERD in percent in relation to GDP - 0.0/97, joint ventures/strategic partnership agreements/billion USD (PPP) in percent in relation to GDP - 0.0/62, patent families/billion USD in percent in relation to GDP - 0.0/90),

third, mastering knowledge-19.0 scores and ranked 98 (intellectual property fees, total sales percentage - 0.3/83, high technology imports, total sales in percent - 8.8/51, ICT services import, total sales in percent - 0.3/115, net inflow of foreign direct investment in percent in relation to GDP - 2.8/58, research potential at enterprises in percent - 12.9/60).

The rating has no strengths in these business attractiveness indicators, with the exception of the business-funded GERD.

The greatest increase we can witness in “Knowledge & technology outputs” of the rating due to 13 scores growth. Our country has improved its position being

ranked 90 in 2020 and achieving the ranking of 77 in 2021. Although this figure should have been even better, but our patents, research and technical articles and the information we quote are not in a position to be proud of.

First, knowledge creation (creative approach) - 10.6 scores or ranked 77 (patents billion dollars (PPP) in percent in relation to GDP, 1.5/47, RST patents/billion USD (RRR), 0.0/98 percent in relation to GDP, utility models /billion USD, in percent in relation to GDP 1.1/22, research and technical articles/billion USD (PPP), 2.1/125 in percent in relation to GDP, h-index of cited documents 4.4/112),

second, the impact of knowledge - 35.1 scores or ranked 42 in the rating! (labor productivity growth in percent - 4.6/8, new businesses - 1.6/63, software costs, in percent in relation to GDP - no data available, ISO 9001 quality certificates/billion USD (PPP) in relation to GDP - 2.3/83, high-tech production, in percent - 24.0/52),

third, the spread of knowledge - 8.0 scores or ranked 102 in the rating (revenues on the object of intellectual property, 0.0/103 in percent, attractiveness of production and exports 34.4/79, exports of high technologies, 0.1/119 in percent in relation to the overall trade, exports of ICT services, in percent in relation to overall trade - 0.8/87). On the basis of the reforms ongoing in the socio-economic areas of the country, the emergence of business entities and their high labor productivity deserves a high ranking in the international ratings. That is, our country has been ranked 8 in terms of the labor productivity growth! (For comparison: Republic of Belarus ranked 38, Russia ranked 44, Kazakhstan-48), in percent - 4.6/8. In addition, favourable position can be observed in terms of the conditions created for the performance of new businesses. We can confidently ascertain that the analytical data presented in these indicators have shown their strengths.

In the seventh indicator “Creative outputs” Uzbekistan has improved by 14 scores (ranked 113 in 2021 and 127 in 2020). At the same time, it has reached 12.3 scores in the rating.

first, intangible assets have been assessed at 19.0 scores or data have not been fully developed [106] (on trademarks/billion USD (PPP) in relation to GDP 32.8/71, global brand value with the highest value of 5000, in GDP - no data available, on industrial samples/billion USD (PPP), in relation to GDP - 1.0/69, ICT and organizational modeling - no data available),

second, creative goods and services -5.9 scores or ranked 101 in the rating (export of cultural and creative services, in percent to total trade - 0.0/95, national feature films - 4.2/47, entertainment and media market - no data available, printing and other media, production as a percentage - 0.7/79, exports of creative products, as a percentage of total trade - 0.2/86),

third, online creativity - 5.3 scores or ranked 122 in the rating (total top-level domains (TLDs) - 0.0/131, country code TLD - 1.1/82, wikipedia edits - 23.7/116, mobile application creation/billion USD (RRR), in relation to GDP - 0.0/99).

It should be noted, we still have a lot of work to do on these indicators. However, we are still far behind the foreign experience in the creation and commercialization of intellectual property (creation of intellectual property ecosystem), which has been repeatedly mentioned by the President of our country. Moreover, the President has determined it as one of the priorities.

We can say with confidence that today, on the basis of the “Third Renaissance”, the “Concept of Science Development until 2030”, adopted as one of the important steps in achieving international indexes and rankings of Uzbekistan, is being implemented. It is not difficult to understand this, as we are gradually rising in the above International rankings because in 2020, when we scored the International Innovation Index (GII) by this World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), in 2021, it was ranked 86.

Conclusion

Currently the funds allocated for science and research in Uzbekistan account for only 0.5 percent of the national GDP. This figure is much lower than the funds allocated to science by developed and developing countries. In addition, the level of commercialization of research results is not high. It is noted that this does not enable research institutions and innovative enterprises established by them to attract investment and bank loans. As a result, by 2030, some low-rated indicators will need to be improved in order to rank high in the Global Innovation Index rankings. In this case, we consider it necessary to pay attention to the following aspects:

first, increase the research and development expenses on the component of human capital and research, as well as the development of technology transfer;

second, to further improve the performance of foreign-funded (GERD) indicators on the business attractiveness component and to develop ICT services;

third, to further increase and develop the dissemination of knowledge on the science and technology outcome component;

fourth, to further improve Internet creativity and mobile application development on the creative outcomes component.

The period of the “Third Renaissance”, which began in new Uzbekistan, has never yet been included in the international rankings and indices, in particular: Global Competitiveness Index, World Economic Forum, INSEAD international business-school, Cornell University, World Intellectual Property Organization, (WIPO), Global Green Economy Index - Dual Citizen LLC organization, as well as Competitive Industrial Performance Index developed by United Nations Industrial

Development Organization (UNIDO), however, in future our country is striving to get high ranking in the assessment of this reputable ranking agencies.

Despite the impact of the global pandemic, in accordance with the “Concept of Science Development until 2030” and the “Third Renaissance” launched in our country, it is crucially important to intensify and develop activities aimed at raising the number of published research articles, citation index, participation in international conferences and seminars, research activities of higher education institutions on the basis of state support of higher education institutions.

Uzbekistan has already undertaken its first steps in the Global Innovation Index (GII) rating, which has been recognized by reputable international organizations.

In conclusion, the experience of the past two years have shown that Uzbekistan has succeeded in achieving a worthy rating in the Global Innovation Index alongside with economically developed countries, which development history accounts for several hundred years. Following this active development rates, no doubt, will result in achieving the goals and objectives set in the Concept of development of Uzbekistan by 2030. After all, as our President said, aspiration to research is in our blood and in our genes.

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